

Repository Profile:

University of Glasgow: "Enlighten" IR & Research System

Current system interoperability areas

The default approach to CRIS/IR interoperability covers four main areas, all of them based on metadata exchange between both systems: bibliographic metadata exchange for publications to be stored in the repository, funded project metadata transfer, financial information exchange and research data metadata exchange. This case study examines how these four operations are carried out at the University of Glasgow, one of the world-leading institutions in research information management. Two main systems, the Enlighten institutional repository and the Research System are used at the University of Glasgow as described above.

In 2010 metadata and information exchange between these two systems was enabled, such that the University of Glasgow have managed to enhance the information attached to specific institutional publications with associated funding information. The Enlighten repository is becoming increasingly capable of reporting to funder systems such as RCUK's Research Outcomes System² thus providing a best practice example for the IR-as-CRIS use case described in the [classification for institutional system configurations](#).

¹ Built with a consortium of organisations under the Management and Administrative Computing (MAC) initiative: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User:Lisbk/MAC_Initiative. U Glasgow were amongst a minority who sustained and customised the resulting system.

² The functionality that enables information exchange with the RCUK Outcomes System is currently unavailable due to RCUK adopting a new system, interoperability with research organisation systems is timetabled for discussion.

Enlighten EPrints based IR

- Developed from the JISC funded DAEDALUS Project (2002-5)
- Holds 72,000 items as of September 2014 (mostly metadata-only records, current full-text percentage 11%) for institutional peer-reviewed journal articles, published conference papers, books and book chapters
- A second repository is available for institutional theses and dissertations

Research System at UofG

- Originally est 1994
- In-house-built system¹ holding research information for institutional research activity, incl people, organisations, projects and outputs
- Dynamically linked to the Enlighten IR
- Currently being updated to an enhanced platform (with same basic functionality) based on a commercial product (due around March 2015).

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1. Bibliographic metadata exchange automatically captured from international databases

Some organisations harvest bibliographic metadata for institutional publications directly from international databases like Web of Science and Scopus into their Research Information Management System/CRIS and thence onto their institutional repository. The process for automated bibliographic metadata collection carried out for Enlighten is slightly different, with the import of records by DOI in many cases taken from searches from databases such as Web of Science and Scopus. As these records are imported their DOIs are checked against existing records to identify duplicates. These imported records are reviewed by library staff and linked to Glasgow authors before being made publicly available.

The screenshot shows the 'Research System' interface. It includes a navigation menu on the left with options like 'Search', 'Create Project', 'Outstanding Actions', 'Report List', 'Personal Settings', 'System Versions', 'Help', 'Feedback', and 'Exit RS'. The main content area displays a 'Welcome to the Research System' message with a version number of v4.05.32 and a release date of 23/7/2014. Below the message is a table of 'Recently Accessed Projects' with columns for ID, Title, and Lead. The table lists several projects, including 'The Protonemerosity TH2 Response as a Therapeutic Target...', 'Photography, transmission dynamics and pathogenesis of B...', 'EPRAC - Using Data about Research Outcomes to Inform Care...', 'ESRC Doctoral Training Centre 2011...', 'The application of a high-throughput NMR metabolomics system...', 'Responsive PhD (Substrate)...', 'MATCH-UP: matching under preferences - algorithms and compl...', 'Algorithms of Stable Matching Problems with Inference...', 'The medical Stackoverflow: Literature and Science in Roman...', and 'The Scottish Research Partnership in Engineering (SRPE)...'. At the bottom, there are input fields for 'Project ID' and 'Award ID' with a 'Go' button, and a section for 'Alternative Roles'.

The screenshot shows the 'Enlighten' repository interface. It features a search bar at the top right with a search button. Below the search bar is a 'Quick Search: Authors, Title, Keywords and Fulltext' section with a search button. The main content area is divided into several sections: 'Enlighten' (with a navigation menu), 'Browse Papers by' (with filters for Year, Subject, Journal, Research Funder, College/Schools, and My Enlighten), 'Open Access' (with a list of open access items), and 'University Publications Policy' (with a text block about the policy). The interface is clean and professional, with a blue and white color scheme.

2. Metadata transfer for project/award information

Metadata about research activity including funder, funder's award number, and internal project and award number combination is imported from our Research System and surfaced in the repository. Linking this data together enables us to use the repository to manage compliance reporting to funders (e.g. [RCUK report on Open Access compliance](#), Sep 2014). The funding data is auto-completed in Enlighten from a locally held XML file, which maps to a funder multi-value field. This data is exported from the Research System and imported into the IR on a nightly basis, thus relieving staff from the need to manually complete any of this additional information. Having the repository use the funding data helps with quality of data on the Research System too – e.g. award numbers were all double checked and any typos fixed for RCUK reporting, Grants and contracts staff diligently include the correct funder reference for new awards.

3. Financial information on open access costs

Institutions where integrated CRISs and Financial Systems are run may be able to directly transfer financial information on Open Access costs into the CRIS/IR once some issues are solved. We currently work by transferring information from the Financial system to Enlighten. We have added a few fields to the repository, but at the moment they need to be hand keyed from an extract from our Finance System. There is critically **no unique id on the finance transactions** to match to the actual publication. We need to manually check the records and then use the Finance transaction as the "unique" identifier to cross link the two systems. There are many details that need to be addressed e.g. multiple rows for the same transaction and the way VAT is independently dealt with. We currently have various metadata elements for OA. A standard metadata profile is being shaped via the CASRAI UK OA Working Group¹ using input from the [End-to-End OA project](#)².

4. Research Data Management (RDM)

The University of Glasgow has put in place a range of support for RDM. We have a Data Registry which includes metadata complying with the DataCite specification and linked to external platforms when the data is not stored at the University. CRIS/IR interoperability is applied to this area in the same way as the main EPrints database. We have retained as much as possible of the same functionality whilst tailoring it for datasets. We have been investigating options for, and need to do further work to ensure that datasets are linked to publications and vice versa. The [CRIS2014 presentation](#) "Research data meets research information management: Two case studies using (a) Pure CERIF-CRIS and (b) EPrints repository platform with CERIF extensions" provides some hints on how system interoperability may support RDM for different institutional system configurations. For more information on the University of Glasgow system configuration contact research-openaccess@glasgow.ac.uk.

3 http://www.jisc.ac.uk/whatwedo/programmes/di_researchmanagement/researchinformation/casraipilot.aspx

4 <http://e2eo.org/>